

Synthesis of 12-ethoxy-3-oxo-4-phenylquino[3,2-*c*][1,3]diazocines via Vilsmeier-Haack reaction

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Application of Vilsmeier condition on 4-hydroxyquinaldines give potentially useful intermediates 4-chloro-3-formyl-2-(2-hydroxyethene-1-yl)quinolines, which are utilized to prepare quino[3,2-*c*][1,3]diazocines on treatment with *N*-phenylurea.

In recent past there has been a widespread interest on the application of Vilsmeier reagent in organic syntheses. Earlier reports reveal the reagent to be a mild and efficient formylating agent for reactive aromatic and heteroaromatic substrates¹. The versatility of the reaction has been further extended as an activating agent for acylhalo addition² and ring annulation³. Moreover, a wide variety of alkene derivatives⁴, carbonyl compounds⁵, activated methyl and methylene groups⁶ as well as oxygen and nitrogen nucleophiles⁷ efficiently react with Vilsmeier-Haack reagent to yield the corresponding iminium salts. The intramolecular cyclization potential of halomethyleniminium salts formed under Vilsmeier condition and microwave induced Vilsmeier conditions have been reported⁸. The classical Vilsmeier-Haack reaction involves electrophilic substitution of an activated aromatic ring with a halomethyleniminium salt to yield the corresponding iminium species, which facilitates easy entry into large number of novel heterocyclic systems.

The capability of the reagent to generate a broad spectrum of iminium species has been explored further for the construction of [*c*]annelated nitrogen and oxygen heterocycles via 4-chloro-3-formylquinaldines obtainable from 4-hydroxyquinaldines⁹ by Vilsmeier-Haack reaction.

Results and discussion

It was presumed that the Vilsmeier-Haack reaction on 4-hydroxyquinaldines (**1**) (previously prepared from corresponding aniline and ethyl acetoacetate followed by subsequent cyclization of the β -anilino crotonates) could provide a utility intermediate for the preparation of several substituted [*c*]annelated heterocyclic compounds¹⁰. The reaction was carried out at 100^o for 15–20 h, using the Vilsmeier-Haack reagent derived from phosphorus oxychloride-

dimethylformamide *in situ*. The reaction yielded a mixture of products, which were separated by using silica gel column chromatography. The analytical and spectroscopic data confirmed the products as 4-chloro-3-formyl-2-(2-hydroxyethene-1-yl)quinoline (**2**), 4-hydroxy-3-formylquinaldine (**3**) and 4-chloroquinaldine (**4**) in good yields (Scheme 1).

- 1-4 : (a) R₁ - R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H
(b) R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H
(c) R₂ = CH₃, R₁ = R₃ = R₄ = H
(d) R₃ = Cl, R₁ = R₂ = R₄ = H
(e) R₁ = R₄ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H

Scheme 1

The reaction of Vilsmeier reagent on 4-hydroxyquinaldines (**1**) at 100^o resulted in the formation of 4-chloro-3-formyl-2-(2-hydroxyethene-1-yl)quinolines (**2a-e**), which could be further utilized for the construction of a novel nitrogen heterocyclic ring system.

The Vilsmeier-Haack reagents are usually applied for the formylation of aromatic and heteroaromatic compounds. These are the chloromethyleniminium species responsible for the formylation (Scheme 2). As in our reaction, the chloromethyleniminium species obtained *in situ*

from phosphorus oxychloride-dimethylformamide react with the active methyl group of 4-hydroxyquinoline (1) to yield 6. Another formylation occurs at the aromatic C₇ of the quinoline leading to the iminium compound 8. Since

Scheme 2

these iminium salts have the special ability to replace the hydroxyl group at aromatic C₄ by the nucleophiles like chlorine, bromine etc., they have led to the formation of 4-chloroquinoline (4) in minor yields and also to the replacement of hydroxy group by the chloro group forming 4-chloro-3-formyl-2-(2-hydroxyethene-1-yl)quinoline (2) in

- 2,11,12 (a) R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H
 (b) R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H
 (c) R₂ = CH₃, R₁ = R₃ = R₄ = H
 (d) R₁ = Cl, R₁ = R₂ = R₄ = H
 (e) R₁ = R₄ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H

Scheme 3

the case of 4-hydroxyquinoline (1a) and 8-methyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1b), the reaction was completed within 15 h and with 5,8-dimethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1e), in 20 h as monitored by the TLC

Having prepared the new intermediates, 2a-e we were able to carry out the intended synthesis of some annulated

quinolines. The vinyl derivative was treated with *N*-phenylurea in alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution and refluxed for two hours. After the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was poured onto crushed ice and extracted with ethyl acetate. The silica gel column chromatography of the extract afforded the desired compounds 12a-e using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate as the eluents (Scheme 3).

The reaction proceeded via the corresponding *N*-phenylhydrazone. Subsequent cyclization yielded the diazocine. The yields, reaction time and the temperature at which the reaction was carried out are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Vilsmeier-Haack reaction on 4-hydroxyquinolines (1a-e) and synthesis of quino[3,2-c][1,3]diazocines (12a-e)

Compd no	Reaction time (h)	Yields (%)			
		2	3	4	12
1a	15	70	15	10	–
1b	12.5	73.5	18	5	–
1c	16	55	12	17	–
1d	17.5	78	12	5	–
1e	20	65	10	15	–
2a	1.5	–	–	–	68
2b	2	–	–	–	72
2c	2.5	–	–	–	65
2d	2	–	–	–	55
2e	3	–	–	–	75

Experimental

Thin layer chromatography was used to monitor the reactions and the purity of products. M.ps. were determined on a Boetius Microheating table (Japan) and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 FT spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AMX-400 MHz spectrometer with TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer (70 eV). C, H, N analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 240 analyser.

General procedure .

Vilsmeier-Haack reaction on 4-hydroxyquinoline : The Vilsmeier reagent was prepared by taking *N,N*-dimethylformamide (3.86 ml, 0.05 mol) at 0–5°. Phosphorus oxychloride (13.04 ml, 0.014 mol) was added to it dropwise over a period of 30 min with constant stirring and the resultant mixture was stirred for another 1 h. The appropriate 4-hydroxyquinoline (1a-e) was added to the Vilsmeier reagent. The mixture was stirred for 30 min at RT and was then kept on a water-bath at 100° for the period of time stated in Table 1. After the reaction was over (monitored through TLC), the reaction mixture was poured onto crushed ice (500 g) with constant stirring and set aside

overnight. The precipitate obtained on neutralization with 4 *N* NaOH was washed with water and extracted using ethyl acetate. The silica gel chromatography of ethyl acetate soluble product afforded three compounds **4**, **3** and **2** using petroleum ether, petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (94 : 6) and petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (85 : 15), respectively. The products were recrystallized with methanol and were identified by the analytical and spectroscopic data.

12-Ethoxy-3-oxo-4-phenylquino[3,2-c][1,3]diazocines :

To an alcoholic solution of KOH (15%; 50 ml), *N*-phenylurea (0.002 mol) and appropriate 4-chloro-3-formyl-2-(2-hydroxyethene-1-yl)quinoline (0.002 mol) were added and the mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 h. The excess ethanol was then removed under reduced pressure, cooled and poured onto crushed ice. Precipitate obtained was extracted with ethyl acetate and the silica gel column chromatography of the extract yielded the desired products :

2a m.p. 155°. C₁₂H₈O₂NCl (Found : C, 61.62; H, 3.38; N, 5.92. calcd. for : C, 61.69; H, 3.45; N, 5.99%); δ_H 7.7 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, C₈-H), 7.6 (1H, t, *J* 8.3 Hz, C₇-H), 7.9 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz, C₆-H), 8.2 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, C₅-H) 9.2 (1H, s, C₃-CHO), 9.4, 9.6 (2H, 2s, vinylic protons), 16.5 (vinylic-OH, bs, D₂O exchangeable); δ_C 192.419, 189.332, 189.08, 146.24, 137.30, 135.90, 133.32, 126.93, 125.21, 122.61, 119.32, 118.99; *m/z* (M⁺) 233, (M+2) 235; ν_{max} 3438, 1664, 1595 cm⁻¹. **3a** m.p. 140°. C₁₁H₉O₂N (Found : C, 70.54; H, 4.81; N, 7.43. calcd. for : C, 70.58; H, 4.85; N, 7.48%) δ_H 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.3 (1H, d, *J* 7.84 Hz, C₅-H), 7.5 (1H, t, *J* 7.58 Hz, C₇-H), 7.7 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, C₆-H), 8.2 (1H, d, *J* 8.28 Hz, C₅-H), 9.4 (1H, s, CHO), 14.1 (1H, bs, OH); *m/z* (M⁺) 187; ν_{max} 3520, 1695, 1610 cm⁻¹. **4a** m.p. 65°. δ_H 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.3 (1H, s, C₃-H), 8.1 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, C₅-H), 7.7 (1H, t, *J* 7.54 Hz, C₆-H), 7.9 (1H, t, *J* 7.82 Hz, C₇-H), 7.5 (1H, d, *J* 8.14 Hz, C₈-H); ν_{max} 1590 cm⁻¹. **12a** m.p. 214°. C₂₁H₁₇N₃O₂ (Found : C, 73.32; H, 4.85; N, 12.31. calcd. for : C, 73.45; H, 4.99; N, 12.24%); δ_H 1.35 (3H, t, *J* 7.24 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, *J* 7.10 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 6.8–8.2 (11H, m, Ar-H), 9.1 (1H, s, C₁-H); *m/z* (M⁺) 343; ν_{max} 1550, 1585, 1620 cm⁻¹.

2b m.p. 132°. C₁₃H₁₀O₂NCl (Found : C, 62.02; H, 3.98; N, 5.63. calcd. for : C, 63.04; H, 4.07; N, 5.66%); δ_H 2.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.5 (1H, t, *J* 7.92 Hz, C₆-H), 7.7 (1H, d, *J* 7.16 Hz, C₇-H), 8.1 (1H, d, *J* 8.24 Hz, C₅-H), 9.2 (1H, s, C₃-CHO), 9.4, 9.5 (2H, 2s, vinylic protons), 16.5 (vinylic-OH, bs, D₂O exchangeable); δ_C 192.359, 189.451, 189.014, 147.224, 136.948, 133.953, 130.233, 126.611, 126.390, 122.993, 121.964, 118.594, 18.459; *m/z* (M⁺) 247 (16.5%), (M+2) 249 (5.2%), 220 (66.7%), 203 (100%), 178 (36.5%); ν_{max} 3450, 1660, 1595 cm⁻¹; **3b** m.p. 195°. C₁₂H₁₁O₂N

(Found : C, 71.58; H, 5.44; N, 6.98. calcd. for : C, 71.63; H, 5.51; N, 6.96%); δ_H 2.6 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 7.4 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, C₆-H), 7.6 (1H, d, *J* 7.28 Hz, C₇-H), 8.0 (1H, d, *J* 8.24 Hz, C₅-H), 9.3 (1H, s, CHO), 15.3 (1H, bs, OH); *m/z* (M⁺) 201; ν_{max} 3500, 1710, 1590 cm⁻¹. **4b** m.p. 47°. δ_H 2.7 (3H, s, C₂-CH₃), 2.8 (3H, s, C₈-CH₃), 7.4 (1H, s, C₃-H), 8.1 (1H, d, *J* 7.92 Hz, C₅-H), 7.4 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, C₆-H), 7.6 (1H, d, *J* 6.28 Hz, C₇-H); ν_{max} 1570 cm⁻¹. **12b** m.p. 235°. C₂₂H₁₉N₃O₂ (Found : C, 73.84; H, 5.26; N, 11.71. calcd. for : C, 73.93; H, 5.36; N, 11.76%); 1.6 (3H, t, *J* 7.02 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 2.7 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.4 (2H, q, *J* 6.96 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 7.1–8.0 (10H, m, Ar-H), 8.5 (1H, s, C₁-H); *m/z* (M⁺) 357; ν_{max} 1565, 1593, 1630 cm⁻¹.

2c m.p. 148°. C₁₃H₁₀O₂NCl (Found : C, 62.98; H, 4.01; N, 5.59. calcd. for : C, 63.04; H, 4.07; N, 5.66%); δ_H 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.6 (1H, d, *J* 7.56 Hz, C₆-H), 7.8 (1H, s, C₈-H), 8.1 (1H, d, *J* 8.16 Hz, C₅-H), 9.2 (1H, s, CHO), 9.3, 9.5 (2H, 2s, vinylic protons), 16.5 (vinylic-OH, bs, D₂O exchangeable); δ_C 192.28, 189.41, 189.09, 145.26, 135.68, 134.06, 131.22, 126.28, 126.05, 122.75, 122.34, 119.70, 19.52; *m/z* (M⁺) 247 (M+2) 249; ν_{max} 3480, 1670, 1590 cm⁻¹. **3c** m.p. 215°. C₁₂H₁₁O₂N (Found : C, 71.61; H, 5.46; N, 6.94. calcd. for : C, 71.63; H, 5.51; N, 6.96%); δ_H 2.5 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 7.6 (1H, d, *J* 7.14 Hz, C₆-H), 7.8 (1H, s, C₈-H), 8.0 (1H, d, *J* 8.20 Hz, C₅-H), 9.4 (1H, s, CHO), 15.1 (1H, bs, OH); *m/z* (M⁺) 201; ν_{max} 3350, 1700, 1600 cm⁻¹. **4c** m.p. 92°. δ_H 2.6 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 7.3 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.5 (1H, s, C₈-H), 7.8 (1H, d, *J* 7.24 Hz, C₆-H), 8.1 (1H, d, *J* 8.06 Hz, C₅-H); ν_{max} 1585 cm⁻¹. **12c** m.p. 187°. C₂₂H₁₉N₃O₂ (Found : C, 73.78; H, 5.48; N, 11.85. calcd. for : C, 73.93; H, 5.36; N, 11.76%); δ_H 1.55 (3H, t, *J* 7.18 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 2.6 (1H, s, CH₃), 4.5 (2H, q, *J* 6.98 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 7.3–8.2 (10H, m, Ar-H), 8.7 (1H, s, C₁-H); *m/z* (M⁺) 357; ν_{max} 1558, 1590, 1633 cm⁻¹.

2d m.p. 180°. C₁₂H₇O₂NCl₂ (Found : C, 53.71; H, 2.65; N, 5.22. calcd. for : C, 53.76; H, 2.63; N, 5.26%); δ_H 7.3 (1H, d, *J* 7.68 Hz, C₇-H), 7.5 (1H, d, *J* 7.96 Hz, C₈-H), 8.1 (1H, s, C₅-H), 9.2 (1H, s, C₃-CHO), 9.3, 9.5 (2H, 2s, vinylic protons), 16.5 (vinylic-OH, bs, D₂O exchangeable); δ_C 192.27, 189.26, 189.08, 133.90, 133.21, 129.80, 129.04, 124.41, 121.13, 120.86, 119.87, 118.34; *m/z* (M⁺) 267, (M+2) 269, (M+4) 271; ν_{max} 3470, 1670, 1590 cm⁻¹. **3d** m.p. 230°. C₁₁H₈O₂NCl (Found : C, 59.52; H, 3.57; N, 6.27. calcd. for : C, 59.61; H, 3.64; N, 6.32%); δ_H 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.4 (1H, d, *J* 8.76 Hz, C₇-H), 7.7 (1H, d, *J* 7.64 Hz, C₈-H), 8.2 (1H, s, C₅-H), 9.4 (1H, s, CHO), 14.2 (1H, bs, OH); *m/z* (M⁺) 221; ν_{max} 3480, 1715, 1595 cm⁻¹. **4d** m.p. 74°. δ_H 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.4 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.7–8.0 (3H, m, Ar-H); ν_{max} 1575 cm⁻¹. **12d** m.p. 168°. C₂₁H₁₆N₃O₂Cl

Note

(Found : C, 66.71; H, 4.18; N, 11.23. calcd. for : C, 66.76; H, 4.27; N, 11.12%); δ_{H} 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.10 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 4.3 (2H, q, J 7.28 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 7.2–7.9 (10H, m, Ar-H), 8.5 (1H, s, C_1 -H); m/z (M^+) 377, ($\text{M}+2$) 379; ν_{max} 1565, 1580, 1625 cm^{-1} .

2c m.p. 170°. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ (Found : C, 64.21; H, 4.57; N, 5.28. calcd. for : C, 64.25; H, 4.62; N, 5.35%); δ_{H} 2.6 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.6 (1H, d, J 7.46 Hz, C_6 -H), 7.9 (1H, d, J 7.96 Hz, C_7 -H), 9.3 (1H, s, CHO), 9.4, 9.5 (2H, 2s, vinylic protons), 16.5 (vinylic-OH, bs, D_2O exchangeable); δ_{C} 192.34, 189.38, 189.07, 144.34, 136.38, 133.86, 130.95, 127.54, 126.01, 123.11, 122.45, 118.60, 19.80, 18.95; m/z (M^+) 261, ($\text{M}+2$) 263; ν_{max} 3525, 1680, 1595 cm^{-1} . **3e** m.p. 155°. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ (Found : C, 72.47; H, 6.01; N, 6.42. calcd. for : C, 72.54; H, 6.09; N, 6.51%); δ_{H} 2.7 (9H, s, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.5 (1H, d, J 7.84 Hz, C_6 -H), 7.7 (1H, d, J 7.68 Hz, C_7 -H), 9.2 (1H, s, CHO), 14.5 (1H, bs, OH); m/z (M^+) 215; ν_{max} 3510, 1702, 1610 cm^{-1} . **4e** m.p. 80°. δ_{H} 2.6 (9H, s, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.4 (1H, s, C_3 -H), 7.6–7.8 (2H, m, Ar-H); ν_{max} 1580 cm^{-1} . **12d** m.p. 22°. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ (Found : C, 74.28; H, 5.82; N, 11.27. calcd. for : C, 74.37; H, 5.70; N, 11.31%); δ_{H} 1.5 (3H, t, J 7.12 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.6 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 4.4 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 7.1–7.8 (9H, m, Ar-H), 8.6 (1H, s, C_1 -H); m/z (M^+) 371; ν_{max} 1550, 1587, 1633 cm^{-1} .

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